

Understanding Climate-Driven Migration: A Bayesian Analysis of Household Income and Livelihood Strategies in Rural Nepal

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August 24, 2025

[Original working draft v1 / Un-peer-reviewed]

“By natural order, birthing needs good timing and at a moderate pace. [...] Looking for food in the fields and gardens farther from home is important. Also, try eating different kinds of nuts and worms. Mastering all of this would guarantee a prosperous life.”

—In “Food”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

Abstract

Smallholder farmers in climate-sensitive regions face increasing environmental variability, economic marginalization, and limited institutional support, which shape their adaptive strategies. Migration—both seasonal and long-term—has emerged as a critical response. This study investigates how household income and livelihood composition influence migration decisions in Sudurpaschim Pradesh, Nepal, using Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) and the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF). Drawing on survey data from 327 households, the analysis distinguishes between seasonal non-farm migration as a short-term coping strategy and long-term off-farm migration intention as a forward-looking adaptation pathway. We found that household earning is positively associated with seasonal migration, but the association is alleviated if the income is derived primarily from livestock, consistent with livestock's buffering and location-bound returns. By contrast, long-term migration intentions depend less on total income and more on income sources and associated vulnerability. High-income households that are reliant on food self-sufficiency or cereal/crop sales are more likely to have long-term migration intentions, whereas those reliant on livestock are less likely—reflecting higher opportunity costs and relative stability. Overall, seasonal migration appears to be a short-term, income-responsive coping strategy, while long-term intentions reflect deeper interactions among livelihood vulnerability, aspirations/capabilities, and structural conditions. Policies should prioritize high-Nature Quotient adaptation strategies, including climate-resilient diversification, integrated mixed-farming systems, and the development of local value-added enterprises, in order to broaden adaptive options and ensure that migration remains a choice rather than a necessity.

Keywords: Smallholder farmers; seasonal migration; Livelihood composition; Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT)

1. Introduction

In climate-sensitive regions, smallholder farmers experience growing pressures that can affect both livelihoods and food security, often leading them to consider adaptive strategies such as seasonal migration (Kumar et al., 2022). These farmers, who make up a significant share of the agricultural workforce in many developing countries, often operate under precarious conditions—including rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, and shifting growing seasons (Bouteska et al., 2024). Such stressors directly affect crop yields and incomes, while also straining local ecosystems and exacerbating food insecurity (Farooq et al., 2022). For example, extreme heat during pollination can lead to crop failure, compounding livelihood challenges (Schmitt et al., 2022).

In response to these pressures, smallholders adopt diverse coping strategies, ranging from modifying agricultural practices to seeking non-farm income (Aniah et al., 2019). However, the ability to adapt is often constrained by limited access to capital, agricultural inputs, technology, and institutional support (Ojo et al., 2024). These constraints can be more evident in remote or economically marginalized regions, where climate risks intersect with limited infrastructure and governance challenges.

In such contexts, seasonal migration has emerged as a common short-term strategy to stabilize household income, especially during periods of low agricultural productivity or after climate-induced crop failures (Osei-Acheampong & Opoku Mensah, 2024). While migration is often framed as a rational response to environmental shocks, it is also shaped by broader structural conditions such as poverty, market access, and institutional support (de Sherbinin et al., 2022; Mirzabaev et al., 2023). Yet, empirical research remains limited on how specific economic characteristics at the household level—such as income composition or food self-sufficiency—shape these migration decisions, particularly in under-researched regions like western Nepal.

Sudurpaschim Pradesh, located in Nepal's Far Western Region, illustrates the connections between climate vulnerability, economic marginalization, and migration. Farmers in this ecologically diverse region—from flat plains to mountainous hills—face frequent weather variability, soil degradation, and water scarcity (IOM, 2024). Limited access to irrigation, agricultural technology, and financial services contributes to declining yields and unstable incomes. Small landholdings and weak market connectivity exacerbate these challenges, leaving few viable local alternatives for income generation (Lamichhane et al., 2022).

In such settings, seasonal migration—particularly to urban centers in Nepal, India, or the Gulf—has become a widely used livelihood strategy (Thapa Magar et al., 2024). Households often send one or more members to work during agricultural offseasons or following poor harvests. While remittances can provide essential income, this strategy can strain households left behind. Labor shortages during critical farming periods may lead to further productivity loss, while the burden of farm work and caregiving falls disproportionately on women and older family members (Gautam & Andersen, 2016; Simelton et al., 2021).

National initiatives such as the National Adaptation Programme of Action (NAPA) and Local Adaptation Plans of Action (LAPA) are designed to enhance rural resilience, though implementation can be uneven, especially in remote areas with limited resources (Darjee et al., 2021; Regmi et al., 2016). Consequently, some households continue to rely on migration as a form of adaptation when institutional support is limited. This situation can be particularly challenging for marginalized groups, who may face additional barriers in accessing resources and participating in formal adaptation planning (Bishokarma & Sharma, 2013; Dhakal, 2023).

In this context, where environmental pressures, economic vulnerability, and institutional constraints intersect, further empirical understanding of the economic factors influencing migration would be valuable. While income is frequently highlighted as an important factor, it is not yet fully clear how different forms of livelihood — such as food self-sufficiency, cereal farming, or livestock income — relate to household income in shaping migration decisions. Similarly, the extent to which migration serves as a proactive adaptation strategy versus a response to limited local opportunities remains to be explored.

Research Objective

While previous studies have examined broad socioeconomic and environmental factors influencing climate-related migration (Almulhim et al., 2024; Ronco et al., 2023), there is still a limited understanding of household-level economic dynamics in climate-vulnerable and resource-constrained regions. This study explores the role of household income and livelihood strategies in shaping smallholder migration decisions in Sudurpaschim Pradesh. Using Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GIT) and the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF), the research considers how farmers perceive

and weigh economic and environmental trade-offs when deciding whether to migrate. Specifically, the study addresses the following research questions:

1. How do household income and livelihood strategies—including food self-sufficiency, cereal crop income, and livestock income—influence the likelihood of engaging in seasonal non-farm migration as a short-term adaptation strategy?
2. How do the same economic and livelihood factors shape smallholder households' intentions to exit agriculture through long-term off-farm employment?

By examining household-level data from a remote, climate-sensitive region, this study seeks to inform rural adaptation policies that better consider the economic realities smallholder communities face when managing climate risks.

2. Method

2.1. Theoretical foundation

This study is grounded in Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT), an extension of the Mindsponge Theory (MT), which explains how smallholder farmers process climate-related information and form adaptive beliefs (Vuong & Nguyen, 2024a, 2024b). GITT views cognition as a dynamic, entropy-regulating system, integrating insights from information theory (Shannon, 1948) and quantum cognition (Rovelli, 2016). Within this framework, each farmer functions as an information-processing node in a decentralized, collective system, refining signals according to survival needs.

Adaptation under GITT involves a three-stage filtering process: (1) exposure to relevant information, (2) evaluation of livelihood benefits, and (3) subsequent action (Nguyen & Jones, 2022). Environmental threats, such as droughts or pest outbreaks, tend to sharpen farmers' prioritization toward strategies with immediate survival value.

Household income shapes how farmers perceive and assess adaptation options. Higher-income households often have better access to technologies, information, and institutional support, making on-farm adaptation more feasible and potentially reducing the attractiveness of migration. Lower-income households, with fewer local options, may view migration as a more viable strategy. In this sense, income can serve both as a structural factor and as a lens shaping how environmental signals are perceived, which in turn may influence decision-making and risk perception.

Migration, within the GITT framework, is conceptualized not only as a practical livelihood response but also as a cognitive and behavioral strategy to manage environmental stress. Adaptation is understood as an evolving, non-linear process: experiences gained through migration can feed back into local practices, inform community knowledge, and shape future decisions. Social networks established during migration further support the diffusion of information and adaptive strategies within communities.

By combining socio-economic factors, environmental perceptions, and social norms, GITT helps explain why farmers facing similar conditions may adopt different adaptation strategies (Nguyen, 2024). This approach provides a dynamic, context-sensitive perspective on rural climate resilience and decision-making.

2.2. Model Construction

2.2.1. Variable selection and generation

This study draws on an open-access dataset published by Lamichhane et al. (2021), which includes responses from 327 smallholder farmers across all nine districts of Sudurpaschim Pradesh, Nepal. Data were collected through structured household surveys conducted between December 2019 and March 2020, with ethical clearance granted by the Human Ethics Review Committee at Deakin University, Australia. The survey was specifically designed to investigate farmers' perceptions of climate variability and change, their adaptive responses, and the socio-economic and institutional factors that influence adaptation decisions. Key domains included demographic and economic characteristics, agricultural practices, perceived climate risks, and livelihood strategies.

The present analysis focuses on household migration as a form of climate adaptation, emphasizing how household-level economic conditions shape decisions to engage in seasonal non-farm migration (a short-term coping strategy) and long-term off-farm migration (an indicator of longer-term adaptive intent).

To examine the economic determinants of seasonal migration, the first model focuses on a binary outcome variable, *NonFarm_SeasonalMigration*, which indicates whether any household members engaged in seasonal non-farm work during the past year. This variable was derived from a five-point Likert scale assessing the extent of migration practice. Responses were recoded into a binary format as follows: categories 1 ("Not practiced") was coded as 0 (non-migrants), while categories 2 ("Rarely practiced"), 3 ("Practiced in part"), 4 ("Well practiced"), and 5 ("Practiced in full scale") were coded as

1 (migrants). This recoding captures the threshold at which migration becomes a meaningful part of the household's livelihood strategy.

The primary predictor in the model is *HHEarning*, a categorical variable representing household income level, grouped into three categories: Low, Medium, and High. This variable functions as a proxy for household economic capacity and is central to understanding how income influences migration decisions under climate stress. To assess whether different livelihood strategies condition the relationship between income and migration, the model incorporates three binary *moderator variables* that interact with *HHEarning*:

FoodSufficiency: Indicates whether the household is able to meet its food needs through self-produced agricultural goods. This variable reflects a subsistence-based form of resilience, often vulnerable to climate shocks such as drought or crop failure. Households with high food self-sufficiency may therefore rely less on migration even when income is low, as their baseline food security provides a form of stability (Patrick et al., 2025).

CerealCropIncome: Captures whether the household earns income from selling cereal crops (e.g., rice, maize, or wheat). It represents a more market-dependent agricultural strategy that may be sensitive to price volatility and weather-related yield losses. For these households, the incentive to migrate may increase under adverse climate or market conditions (Campbell et al., 2016), and this effect could be amplified or mitigated depending on overall household income.

CashLivestock: Indicates whether the household earns income from selling livestock or poultry. Livestock-based income is generally more flexible and can provide some resilience, as it can be stored, sold when needed, and is often less directly influenced by seasonal climatic changes. Households relying on livestock may therefore be less compelled to migrate, even at lower income levels, because livestock provides both economic and adaptive buffering against environmental shocks (Acosta et al., 2021)

By including these interaction terms, the model examines whether the effect of household income on seasonal migration differs depending on the household's specific livelihood profile. This approach supports the study's aim of understanding how smallholder farmers consider various economic and environmental trade-offs when making migration decisions.

A detailed summary of all variables, coding schemes, and descriptions is provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Variable Descriptions

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Values
<i>HHEarning</i>	Household income level	Categorical	Low, Medium, High
<i>NonFarm_SeasonalMigration</i>	Household engagement in seasonal non-farm migration	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>OffFarm_Migration</i>	Intention or partial engagement in long-term off-farm migration	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>FoodSufficiency</i>	Ability to meet food needs from own production	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>CerealCropIncome</i>	Income from sale of cereal crops	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>CashLivestock</i>	Income from sale of livestock/poultry	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No

2.2.2. Statistical Model

To estimate the effects of household economic status and livelihood characteristics on migration-based adaptation strategies, two separate models were constructed using Bayesian logistic regression under the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF). This approach provides a probabilistic means of understanding belief-driven decision-making in uncertain environments, such as those influenced by climate risks.

Model 1 investigates the probability of actual seasonal non-farm migration, treating it as a short-term coping mechanism. Model 2 focuses on the intention or partial engagement in long-term off-farm migration, representing a forward-looking adaptation strategy. The

inclusion of two models allows for comparison between immediate behavioral responses and latent strategic intentions.

Model 1: Seasonal Non-Farm Migration

This model estimates the likelihood that a household engages in seasonal migration for non-agricultural work, influenced by income level and moderated by livelihood type:

$$NonFarm_SeasonalMigration \sim normal\left(\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right), \sigma\right) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * HHEarning_i + \beta_2 * HHEarning_i * FoodSufficiency_i + \beta_3 * HHEarning_i * CerealCropIncome_i + \beta_4 * HHEarning_i * CashLivestock_i \quad (1.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (1.3)$$

In this model, μ_i represents the expected probability that household i engages in seasonal non-farm migration, predicted based on the values of HHEarning, FoodSufficiency, CerealCropIncome, and CashLivestock. The coefficients β are normally distributed with a mean M and standard deviation S .

Model 2: Long-Term Off-Farm Migration Intention

This model examines households that express intent or partial engagement in long-term off-farm migration. Importantly, full migration is likely underreported due to survey sampling limitations (i.e., migrated individuals no longer present in the household). Therefore, this variable is treated as an indicator of intended rather than actualized migration.

$$OffFarm_Migration \sim normal\left(\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right), \sigma\right) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * HHEarning_i + \beta_2 * HHEarning_i * FoodSufficiency_i + \beta_3 * HHEarning_i * CerealCropIncome_i + \beta_4 * HHEarning_i * CashLivestock_i \quad (2.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (2.3)$$

In this model, μ_i represents the expected probability of long-term off-farm migration intention for household i . Each β coefficient captures the effect of the respective predictor (e.g., household earnings and its interactions with food sufficiency, cereal crop income,

and cash livestock income) on the log-odds of migration intention. The coefficients β are assumed to be normally distributed with mean M and standard deviation S .

In both models, σ denotes the unexplained variability

2.2.3. Data analysis and validation

This study applied the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics, which combines the cognitive structure of Mindsponge Theory (MT) with the inferential strengths of Bayesian statistical modeling (Nguyen et al., 2022; Vuong et al., 2022). The BMF approach is considered well-aligned with research grounded in mental model theories such as MT and GITT, as it accommodates the analysis of complex, belief-based decision-making processes through probabilistic reasoning.

Bayesian inference treats model parameters as probability distributions, making it suitable for estimating models that are both flexible and parsimonious—particularly in exploratory research involving nonlinear relationships or latent cognitive processes (Csilléry et al., 2010; Gill, 2014; Huu et al., 2005). The use of Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods allows for efficient sampling from complex posterior distributions, including those used in multilevel models. Unlike frequentist approaches, Bayesian analysis provides credible intervals instead of p-values, offering alternative insights into parameter uncertainty (Halsey et al., 2015; Wagenmakers et al., 2018). The analyses were carried out using the `bayesvl` R package (La & Vuong, 2019; Van Huu & Hoang, 2007), which provides user-friendly tools for model specification, transparency, and visualisation.

In Bayesian analysis, selecting the appropriate prior is essential during the model construction process. Due to the exploratory nature of this study, uninformative priors or a flat prior distribution were used to provide minimal prior information for model estimation. The Pareto-smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out (PSIS-LOO) diagnostics were employed to check the model’s goodness of fit (Vehtari & Gabry, 2019; Vehtari et al., 2017).

The LOO computation procedure is outlined as follows:

$$LOO = -2LPPD_{loo} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log \int p(y_i|\theta)p_{post(-i)}(\theta)d\theta$$

where $p(y_i|\theta_{-i})$ is the posterior distribution calculated through the data minus data point y_i

The *k-Pareto* values are used in the PSIS method for computing the LOO cross-validation in the R `loo` package. Observations with *k-Pareto* values greater than 0.7 are often considered influential and problematic for accurately estimating LOO cross-validation. If a model's *k* values are less than 0.5, it is typically regarded as a good fit.

If the model fits well with the data, we proceed with the convergence diagnostics and results interpretation. In the current study, we validated the convergence of Markov chains using statistical values and visual illustrations. Statistically, the effective sample size (n_{eff}) and the Gelman–Rubin shrink factor (*Rhat*) can be used to assess convergence. The n_{eff} value represents the number of iterative samples that are not autocorrelated during stochastic simulation, while the *Rhat* value is referred to as the potential scale reduction factor (Brooks & Gelman, 1998). If n_{eff} is larger than 1000, it is generally considered that the Markov chains are convergent, and the effective samples are sufficient for reliable inference (McElreath, 2018). As for the *Rhat* value, if it exceeds 1.1, the model does not converge. The model is considered convergent if *Rhat*=1. Visually, the Markov chains' convergence was also validated using trace plots, Gelman–Rubin–Brooks plots, and autocorrelation plots.

To ensure transparency and facilitate reproducibility, all datasets and code used in this analysis have been deposited in a publicly accessible repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/13859262>.

3. Results

Before interpreting the model estimates, we assessed the predictive performance of Model 1 using the PSIS-LOO diagnostic test. Figure 1 shows that all Pareto *k* values ≤ 0.7 , which indicates a good fit between the model and the dataset.

Figure 1. Model 1's PSIS-LOO diagnosis

Table 2 summarizes the posterior distributions for Model 1, which analyzes the probability of seasonal non-farm migration as a function of household earnings (*HHEarning*) and its interactions with different livelihood strategies. All *Rhat* values equal 1 and effective sample sizes (*n_eff*) exceed 5,000, confirming MCMC convergence and efficiency. The trace plots in Figure 2 also confirm good mixing and convergence for all parameters.

Table 2. Model 1's estimated posterior distribution statistics of household earning parameters (uninformative prior)

Parameters	Mean	SD	n_eff	Rhat
<i>Constant</i>	-0.94	0.79	5423	1
<i>HHEarning</i>	0.29	0.17	5362	1

<i>HHEarning*FoodSufficiency</i>	-0.02	0.05	7813	1
<i>HHEarning*CerealCropIncome</i>	-0.01	0.07	6074	1
<i>HHEarning*CashLivestock</i>	-0.09	0.07	6381	1

Figure 2. Model 1's trace plots

The posterior mean for the main effect of *HHEarning* is 0.29 (SD = 0.17), indicating that higher household income is positively associated with the likelihood of short-term migration. However, the negative coefficient for the *HHEarning*CashLivestock* interaction (-0.09, SD = 0.07) suggests that when higher income is derived from livestock, the

probability of short-term migration decreases. Other interaction terms (*FoodSufficiency*, *CerealCropIncome*) indicate weak or no clear effects.

The 90% Highest Posterior Density Interval (HPDI) for *HHEarning* lies entirely on the positive side of the axis, indicating a highly reliable positive association. In contrast, although a small portion of the HPDI for the interaction term *HHEarning***CashLivestock* extends into the positive range, this segment is negligible. Therefore, the negative association of the interaction term can be regarded as highly reliable.

Figure 3. Model 1’s posterior distributions

3.3 Model 2 – Long-Term Off-Farm Migration Intention

Model 2 examines the intention to migrate long-term for off-farm employment. As noted earlier, this variable is more indicative of migration intention than actual behavior due to sampling limitations. The dataset only includes individuals who reported “not

practiced,” “rarely practiced,” or “practiced in part.” Those who reported “well practiced” or “practiced in full scale” had already migrated and were therefore not available to participate in the survey. Figure 4 displays the *PSIS-LOO* diagnostic for Model 2, with acceptable performance metrics and stable effective sample sizes.

Figure 4. Model 2’s PSIS-LOO diagnosis

Table 3 presents the posterior estimates of Model 2. All n_{eff} and $Rhat$ statistics suggest that the Markov chains are well-convergent. Trace plots in Figure 5 also indicate well-behaved MCMC sampling with no signs of poor convergence.

Table 3. Model 2’s estimated posterior distribution statistics of household earning parameters (uninformative prior)

Parameters	Mean	SD	n_{eff}	$Rhat$
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<i>Constant</i>	-1.83	0.99	4682	1
<i>HHEarning</i>	0.06	0.21	4571	1
<i>HHEarning*FoodSufficiency</i>	0.10	0.06	7369	1
<i>HHEarning*CerealCropIncome</i>	0.10	0.07	6134	1
<i>HHEarning*CashLivestock</i>	-0.13	0.08	7230	1

Figure 5. Model 2's trace plots

The constant term has a posterior mean of -1.83 ($SD = 0.99$), while the main effect of *HHEarning* (mean = 0.06, $SD = 0.21$) is close to zero, with a credible interval that includes zero, indicating no statistically significant association with long-term migration intention.

Unlike Model 1, in Model 2 the source of household income rather than total income shapes long-term migration intentions. Households with higher income from food self-sufficiency or cereal/crop production ($HHEarning*FoodSufficiency = 0.10$, $SD = 0.06$; $HHEarning*CerealCropIncome = 0.10$, $SD = 0.07$) show stronger long-term migration intentions, while households with higher income from livestock ($HHEarning*CashLivestock = -0.13$, $SD = 0.08$) are less likely to intend to migrate, likely reflecting higher opportunity costs and livelihood stability.

As can be seen from Figure 6, HPDIs of $HHEarning*FoodSufficiency$ and $HHEarning*CerealCropIncome$ are almost entirely located on the positive side of the x-axis, suggesting positive moderation effects of *FoodSufficiency* and *CerealCropIncome* on the relationship between *HHEarning* and *OffFarm_Migration*. Meanwhile, the $HHEarning*CashLivestock$ is located entirely on the negative side, implying a highly reliable negative moderation effect.

Figure 6. Model 2's posterior distributions

In summary, Model 1 suggests that higher household earnings are positively associated with short-term migration; however, this effect is alleviated when the household's income is primarily derived from livestock. By contrast, Model 2 indicates that total income alone is not a decisive factor for long-term migration intentions. Instead, the influence depends on income sources: households earning more from food self-sufficiency or cereal/crop production are more likely to have long-term migration intention, whereas those with higher earnings from livestock are comparatively less inclined to do so.

4. Discussion

The analysis highlights distinct patterns in how household earnings and income sources shape migration. For seasonal non-farm migration (Model 1), higher household income

is generally associated with a greater likelihood of migration, though this effect is alleviated when income is primarily derived from livestock. In contrast, long-term migration intentions (Model 2) are influenced less by total income levels and more by the composition of income and the vulnerabilities tied to different livelihoods. Together, these findings suggest that seasonal and long-term migration fulfill different adaptive functions: seasonal migration operates as a short-term, income-responsive coping mechanism, while long-term migration reflects deeper considerations of vulnerability, opportunity costs, and household adaptation strategies.

4.1. Seasonal Migration: Income-Dependent

Model 1 indicates that household earnings positively influence short-term seasonal migration in response to climate stress, but the effect is heterogeneous and shaped by livelihood composition. On average, households with higher incomes are more likely to migrate seasonally. This can be explained by two mechanisms: (i) many migrants take up temporary urban employment, where wages are higher than the rural average (Zhang, 2020), and (ii) higher-income households may have greater capacity to cover migration costs, slightly higher education levels, and wider social networks, which can support their chances of finding urban employment (Ghimire & Kapri, 2023).

However, this positive association weakens when a household's higher income is primarily derived from livestock. In such cases, the probability of seasonal migration decreases, reflecting the relatively lower vulnerability of livestock-based livelihoods to climate variability compared with crop production. Thus, while wealthier households are generally more likely to engage in short-term migration, livestock-dependent households tend to remain in place despite higher earnings.

These findings resonate with the concept of involuntary immobility (Thalheimer et al., 2025). Poorer households, despite being more exposed to climate stress, are often unable to migrate because they lack the financial resources, social capital, or education required to do so. Their immobility is therefore not a matter of choice, but of constrained capacity (Thalheimer et al., 2025). By contrast, livestock-dependent households represent a form of voluntary immobility: although they have the financial means to migrate, they choose to remain in place because their livelihood strategies are more resilient to climate variability (Tanner et al., 2015). This distinction highlights that both migration and immobility can be adaptive responses, depending on household resources and livelihood structures.

4.2 Determinants of Long-Term Migration Intentions.

Model 2 highlights that long-term migration intentions in Nepal are not primarily determined by total household income. Instead, the likelihood of intending to migrate is shaped by the composition of income and the associated vulnerability to climate stress. Households dependent on climate-sensitive sources, such as cereal crops or food self-sufficiency, are more inclined to consider long-term migration. For these households, having adequate financial resources provides the capacity to act, but the vulnerability of their income sources is the main driver motivating migration as a strategy to manage risk and secure future opportunities (Nguyen et al., 2015). Conversely, households with income primarily from livestock demonstrate lower intentions to migrate. Livestock-based livelihoods are generally stable and less affected by climate variability, meaning that migration would involve not only direct costs but also opportunity costs from foregone income (Godde et al., 2021). As a result, these households tend to prioritize maintaining stable, location-bound livelihoods over migration.

It is important to note that these findings reflect migration intentions rather than actual behavior, highlighting aspirations and perceived capabilities rather than realized moves. Additional factors, including education, social networks, labor market opportunities, and structural constraints, further shape households' ability to translate intentions into action (Czaika & Reinprecht, 2020; Gabrielli & Impicciatore, 2022).

Overall, long-term migration intentions appear conditional on livelihood vulnerability and income source rather than total income. Crop-dependent households leverage migration to manage climate-related risks, whereas livestock-dependent households rely on stable local livelihoods. These dynamics not only reinforce the logic of GITT outlined above but also resonate with the Aspirations–Capabilities Framework, which emphasizes that migration outcomes require both motivation (aspiration) and the practical means (capabilities) to move. Taken together, they highlight the complex interplay of economic, environmental, and structural factors in shaping long-term migration decisions (Carling & Collins, 2020; Carling, 2002; De Haas, 2021).

4.3 Synthesis: Seasonal vs. Long-Term Migration in Nepal's Climate-Sensitive Context

Comparing seasonal and long-term migration in Sudurpaschim Pradesh, Nepal, suggests that migration serves different roles in climate-sensitive rural livelihoods. The province experiences frequent floods, droughts, and erratic monsoons, creating both short-term income shocks and longer-term livelihood vulnerabilities. Within this context, seasonal

migration appears to function mainly as a short-term coping strategy, helping households supplement income and manage immediate climate-related risks, while long-term migration reflects more forward-looking decisions influenced by aspirations, structural conditions, and the vulnerability of household livelihoods.

Household livelihood composition and income sources further condition these dynamics. Crop-dependent households, facing high exposure to rainfall variability, may continue to migrate seasonally even at relatively higher income levels, reflecting risk diversification strategies (Warner & Afifi, 2014). By contrast, livestock-dependent households often rely more on in-place coping, as their relatively stable and location-bound returns create higher opportunity costs of migration (Thornton et al., 2007). Long-term migration intentions, therefore, are less directly tied to household income than to the interaction of climate vulnerability, livelihood base, and household capabilities, such as education, social networks, and access to mobility opportunities (Simpson et al., 2024).

In this context, the *Aspirations–Capabilities Framework* provides a useful way to understand migration dynamics (De Haas, 2021). Migration depends not only on households’ desire to move (aspirations) but also on their practical ability to do so (capabilities), including financial resources, education, social networks, access to labor markets, mobility infrastructure, and institutional support. Even when households strongly desire to migrate—for better income, education, or security—they may be constrained by high costs, poor infrastructure, or restrictive policies. This gap between aspiration and ability is referred to as “involuntary immobility”, where households remain in high-risk, climate-sensitive environments despite wanting to move (Zickgraf, 2021).

Using a Bayesian modeling approach allowed us to capture household-specific responses to migration opportunities in Sudurpaschim Pradesh without assuming homogeneity. The model revealed diverse migration strategies across income levels and livelihood types, such as different seasonal migration patterns for crop-dependent versus livestock-dependent households. It also accounted for uncertainty and heterogeneity across groups, reducing the influence of extreme cases. By avoiding strong parametric assumptions, the model naturally highlighted nuanced adaptive responses to Nepal’s climate and livelihood pressures.

5. Policy Implications

The findings highlight the need for context-sensitive policies that account for the heterogeneous effects of income and the moderating role of livelihood composition and

climate vulnerability. In Nepal, seasonal migration varies with income level and livelihood type, with crop-dependent or high-risk households exhibiting greater mobility, reflecting both adaptive strategies and constraints.

Policymakers and development agencies should design interventions that support both seasonal migrants and households constrained in high-risk environments. They can provide financial assistance, build resilient infrastructure, and remove legal or administrative barriers to reduce involuntary immobility, thereby enhancing adaptive capacity and promoting social equity (Black et al., 2011; Nawrotzki & DeWaard, 2018). By addressing both mobility and immobility, these actors align climate adaptation strategies with the needs of all households, emphasizing voluntary migration while protecting those unable to move (Rigaud et al., 2021; Warner & Afifi, 2014).

To strengthen local resilience, policymakers and extension services should promote high-Nature Quotient adaptation strategies such as agricultural diversification, the adoption of climate-resilient crops, and the development of mixed-farming systems (Vuong & Nguyen, 2025; Vuong et al., 2025). In addition, fostering small-scale value-added enterprises can generate local employment opportunities and help reduce dependence on seasonal migration (Antonelli et al., 2022; Lindegaard et al., 2025). They should also improve market access, stabilize household incomes, and develop value chains for livestock and perishable products to buffer households against climate shocks (Kopeć, 2024). Furthermore, local governments and NGOs can implement climate-smart practices—including agroforestry, soil and water conservation, drought-tolerant crops, and access to advisory, financial, and veterinary services—to strengthen household resilience while accounting for environmental and market constraints (Habib et al., 2023).

Long-term migration intentions are shaped less by immediate income than by income sources, structural vulnerabilities, opportunity costs, and personal aspirations. Addressing these factors requires policies that strengthen education, expand vocational training, empower youth, and improve rural infrastructure—including schools, healthcare, transport, and communication networks. In Nepal, technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programs have enhanced rural youth employment and income generation (Adhikari et al., 2023), particularly as the system increasingly aligns with labor market demands (Paudel et al., 2025). Likewise, investments in rural infrastructure—such as roads and agricultural credit—have improved households' adaptive capacity to climate risks (Puri et al., 2022). Governments and development

agencies should manage safe labor migration, support households in using remittances strategically, and create local employment opportunities to enable households to migrate by choice rather than necessity. Agricultural extension services and policymakers should train farmers and implement supportive policies to enhance agricultural practices, strengthen rural livelihoods, and complement migration strategies (Raji et al., 2024). Multisectoral planning teams should coordinate migration, development, and climate adaptation interventions to address the underlying drivers of long-term mobility aspirations, particularly for households constrained by involuntary immobility (Czaika & Weisner, 2025).

Crop-based households facing climate shocks show stronger long-term migration intentions, while livestock-based households remain less mobile due to stable returns. This divergence calls on policymakers to strengthen in-place resilience so that migration is a choice rather than a necessity. Local governments and NGOs can implement context-specific strategies such as agroforestry, organic farming, or small-scale eco-tourism to reduce vulnerability for crop-dependent households while sustaining food security. At the same time, they should recognize the cultural and socio-economic role of livestock in rural Nepal to design adaptation pathways that prevent involuntary immobility. Actively involving local communities in discussions on migration and adaptation can align policies with local priorities and values. The Nature Quotient perspective further emphasizes cultivating human–nature awareness to strengthen adaptive capacity beyond purely technical measures (Vuong & Nguyen, 2025). At the same time, migration can be reframed as a proactive and strategic choice rather than merely a last resort (Mukherjee & Fransen, 2024).

6. Limitations and Future Research

The analysis highlights how different income sources and livelihood types influence household migration decisions. However, several limitations should be noted. First, Model 1 examined actual short-term migration, whereas Model 2 focused on long-term migration intentions. Intentions reflect what households plan or hope to do, which may not align with actual movements, particularly when structural barriers such as involuntary immobility exist. Second, the cross-sectional design prevents assessment of how climate impacts and migration strategies evolve over time. Longitudinal or panel studies provide a clearer picture of how shocks and adaptations unfold. Third, the study's

sample size and regional focus limit generalizability, as local geography, market conditions, and infrastructure can strongly shape migration. Fourth, some important factors—such as cultural norms, household decision-making, gender roles, and social networks—were not included in the models, even though they likely affect both seasonal and long-term migration. Self-reported income and livelihood data may also introduce measurement bias.

Future research can address these gaps in several ways. Integrating qualitative methods helps capture socio-cultural and contextual determinants. Models can explicitly incorporate climate-specific livelihood vulnerabilities, such as crop-versus livestock-dependence. Comparative studies across diverse social and ecological settings increase external validity. Panel studies that track both migration intentions and actual mobility over time provide stronger evidence on how income, livelihoods, and climate stress interact. Such studies can also test the role of involuntary immobility more rigorously and provide practical guidance for designing targeted migration and adaptation policies.

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